

Methodological features of constructing the training process of basketball in physical education clubs in general education schools.

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Abstract. The article examines the issues of planning and improving the pre-competition training of young basketball players and the comprehensive system, features, and structure of training young basketball players.

Keywords: Technique, tactics, general physical training, elements, endurance, general developmental exercises.

Introduction: When planning the training process for students of basketball clubs in physical education clubs in general education schools, the following tasks were solved:

Sets of general developmental and special exercises.	Basketballs, medicine balls, gymnastic seats, ropes, weights, rubber bands, audio equipment, etc.
Mastering the necessary theoretical knowledge about basketball.	Study and improvement of basketball game techniques and tactics.
Formation of skills in applying technical and tactical elements.	Two-sided game in training sessions;
Further training and improvement of the basic technical and tactical elements of basketball.	O‘yinlarda texnik-taktik, individual va jamoaviy harakatlarni qo‘llash qobiliyatini shakllantirish

Stylistic features: The total duration of the lesson was 90 minutes, with 15-20 minutes allocated for the preparatory part, 60-70 minutes for the main part, and 5-10 minutes for the final part.

In basketball clubs, training traditionally begins with group formation, greetings, reporting, checking students according to the club journal, announcing training tasks, and exercises for concentration and emotional mood. Then, for 5-7 minutes, various types of walking, running, jumping, turning, stopping, acceleration were used. In grades X and XI, depending on the degree of training, in the first half of the preparatory part of the lesson, exercises with the ball in motion were used (carrying the ball, passing

the ball from the chest with both hands in pairs from above and below, passing the ball from hand to hand in motion with the hands, passing the ball with one hand from above the shoulder, from the side, from below, etc.). As the improvement progressed, efforts were made to perform the indicated exercises at maximum speed and maximum running speed.

The use of exercises in motion and on the spot in the specified ratio made it possible to achieve high effectiveness in the development of general and special endurance of basketball players.

The sets of general developmental and special exercises in the preparatory part are compiled taking into account the main objectives of the training and should be no less than 2. At the initial stage of the training, the ratio of general developmental and special exercises depended on the preparation of the groups and the training course. When paying more attention to the formation of the first GPD and basic skills, priority was given to exercises of a general developmental nature. In the second and third stages, in the process of game practice and the acquisition of skills and abilities characteristic of basketball players, special exercises prevailed in the preparatory part of the training.

After the completion of running exercises, a set of general developmental and special exercises was performed in the above-mentioned ratio for 7-10 minutes. The number of exercises depends on the planned tasks, but, as a rule, they did not exceed 6-10 basic exercises in 10-12 repetitions. General developmental exercises were performed in the same way for all muscle groups according to the top-down principle. Nevertheless, when performing complexes of exercises of a special and general developmental nature, special attention was paid to warming up muscle groups, on which, taking into account the specifics of this game, the maximum load falls in the main part of the training. First of all, these were the muscles of the hands, fingers, shoulders, elbows, knees, ankle joints, and others. Regardless of the nature of the exercises, they were performed in groups.

At the end of the preparatory part of the training, 2-3 flexibility development exercises were performed at a slow and medium pace. The interval of rest between exercises depended on the tasks and preparation of the training group. In the first stage, it was not less than 1-2 minutes, in the second and third years - 0.5-1 minute. When transitioning from one part of the lesson to another, the duration of rest varied within 3-5 minutes.

In the main part of the training, tasks were solved aimed at general physical development, formation and improvement of special qualities, study of technical-tactical individual, team, and team actions, improvement of game practice, etc. Of the

listed areas of motor activity of basketball players, priority was given to teaching GPT and technical techniques in a general education institution, and in grades 9-10 more attention was paid to the development of special qualities and game practice.

The number of exercises in the main part of the lesson depended on the tasks to be solved and the group's preparedness. In the process of teaching technical and tactical techniques, from 8 to 12 basic and parallel exercises were used. In the process of improvement, their number reached a maximum and reached 20 in one lesson. In the periods of mastering game practice, the number of training and improvement exercises was minimized (3-4), more attention was paid to two-sided play, in the process of which the tasks of practicing technical techniques in game conditions were implemented.

In the implementation of the main tasks of training, the classical sequence was followed: first the technical, then the tactical methods of the game were studied. This applies to both individual, group, and collective actions. When studying defensive and offensive techniques, first of all, technical techniques used in offense (movement technique, jumping, stopping, turning, catching, passing, throwing the ball into the basket with one and two hands, etc.) were mastered. Then they began to study defensive techniques (the player's correct posture when facing an opponent, various variations of movement, snatching, kicking, seizing the ball, blocking, jumping to hit the ball, etc.).

Taking into account the specifics of motor activity aimed at developing the speed-strength qualities, speed, and endurance of basketball players, special classes for the development of strength abilities were included in the program of the training process for this type of physical education.

In the final part of the training, exercises were used for the gradual reduction of physical load and the transition from a state of high emotional excitability to a state of relative rest and the continuation of educational activity. In this section, walking, breathing, and relaxation exercises, along with light running, throwing a ball into the hoop from a stationary position, and others were used as the main means of performing the tasks of the final part of the training. At the end of the lesson, the quality of the work (brief analysis and evaluation) was assessed and concluded, then information was provided about the content of the upcoming lesson.

Assessing the intensity of the physical load, it should be noted that in the preparatory part of the training, the HR is in the range of 120-130 bpm, in the main part - from 130 to 180 bpm (its maximum value, as a rule, is recorded during bilateral games), and in the final part - from 100 to 120 bpm. Studies have shown that the value of this indicator

normalized 3-5 minutes after the training.

When performing exercises in various intensity zones, the volume of physical load was in the following ratio: in the compensatory zone (up to 130 bpm) - 30%, in the aerobic zone (131-150 bpm) - 50%, and in the mixed intensity zone (151-180 bpm) - 20% of useful time. Motor density in the men's group was 60-70%, and in the women's group - 50-60%.

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